

of the salicylaldehyde. This upward shift is due to the maintenance of a ring current arising out of electron delocalisation in the chelate ring.

In case of $\text{Ni}(\text{SalH})_2$, which is a trimer, the aldehydic $\text{C}=\text{O}$ and the phenolic $\text{C}-\text{O}$, both split into two; the aldehydic $\text{C}=\text{O}$ show up at 1 655 and 1 636 cm^{-1} , whereas phenolic $\text{C}-\text{O}$ can be spotted out at 1 355 and 1 322 cm^{-1} . Looking into the crystal structure of $[\text{Ni}(\text{SalH})_2]_3$, it is found that half the oxygen atoms of aldehydic and phenolic ones, are bridged oxygens, *i.e.* one oxygen attached to two Ni^{2+} ions. The other half (6 oxygen atoms, comprising of 3 aldehydic and 3 phenolic oxygen atoms) oxygen atoms are terminal ones, *i.e.* they are attached to only one Ni^{2+} ion. The Co^{2+} -salicylaldehyde is also polynuclear, where two aldehydic $\text{C}=\text{O}$ at 1 655 and 1 627 cm^{-1} and two phenolic $\text{C}-\text{O}$ at 1 354 and 1 321 cm^{-1} have been reported. It can be generalised that in metal salicylaldehydes, when they are monomers, the aldehydic $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ and phenolic $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}}$ show only one normal peak at 1 650 cm^{-1} and 1 320 cm^{-1} , respectively; whereas when it is a polymer with oxygen bridges, both the aldehydic and phenolic frequencies split into two, one at the normal region and the other at a slightly higher frequency. In these polynuclear alkali metal transition metal-salicylaldehydes, the aldehydic $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ and phenolic $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}}$ have been observed not to be in their normal range (Table 1), but invariably higher. This is very suggestive that all these oxygens are bridged ones, bridging the transition metal and, most probably, the alkali metal.

The visible absorption spectrum of $[\text{Ni}(\text{SalH})_2]_3$ shows typical octahedral absorption bands at 450, 600, and 900 nm. The electronic spectra of alkali metal adducts is different in nature and show one strong band at ~ 600 nm with a shoulder at 550 nm; but the two other peaks of $[\text{Ni}(\text{SalH})_2]_3$ are missing. This suggests that the octahedral structure $[\text{Ni}(\text{SalH})_2]_3$ has been converted to tetrahedral structure in its alkali metal adducts. The visible absorption spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\text{SalH})_2]_4$ shows only one band at 550 nm, which is typical of an octahedral cobalt (II) complex. In its alkali metal adducts, this 550 nm band of $\text{Co}(\text{SalH})_2$ shift to ~ 650 nm. It is very likely that octahedral $[\text{Co}(\text{SalH})_2]_4$ break up into tetrahedral structure in its alkali metal adducts.

The magnetic properties and electronic spectral studies of alkali metal adducts reveal a break in polymerised system of $[\text{Ni}(\text{SalH})_2]_3$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{SalH})_2]_4$. Accordingly, the octahedral structure of polymeric nickel-salicylaldehyde and cobalt-salicylaldehyde are converted into a tetrahedral structure of $\text{Ni}(\text{SalH})_2$ and $\text{Co}(\text{SalH})_2$ in their alkali metal adducts. The bonding between salicylaldehyde $\text{M}(\text{SalH})_2$ and alkali metal salts, is most likely through the oxygen atoms of aldehydic and phenolic groups, tetrahedrally situated in these cases.

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Highly unsaturated ' N_2O_3 ' Ligand System and its Transition Metal Complexes

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THE synthesis of some of the ' N_2O_3 ' type ligands involve the condensation of β -diketones like acetylacetone, substituted acetylacetone, benzoylacetone, dibenzoylmethane, dipivaloylmethane, 3,5-heptanedione *etc.*¹⁻⁴, with aliphatic diamines. However, there are not many reports on the synthesis of the Schiff base ligands with γ -diketones. The conjugated azomethines are considered to be significant because of their relevance to biologically important processes. Rhodopsin, a compound containing conjugated azomethine, is an important intermediate involved in the chemistry of vision⁵. There has been considerable interest in the synthesis and study of quadridentate Schiff base complexes with ' N_2O_3 ' donors^{6,7}. The stereochemistry of the metal complexes of these ligands is found to vary with the length of the methylene chain⁸. The present investigation aims at the synthesis and characterisation of a highly unsaturated ligand derived from benzilmonohydrazone and a γ -diketone, *viz.* acetylacetone and its nickel(II), copper(II) and cobalt(II) complexes.

Experimental

5,8-Dimethyl-1,2,11,12-tetraphenyl-3,4,9,10-tetrazadodeca-2,4,8,10-tetraen-1,12-dione (DTTHD): Benzilmonohydrazone (BMH) (15 g) was dissolved in dry benzene (100 ml) and acetylacetone (8 ml) was added to it and heated under reflux on a water-bath for 12 h. The dark red solution was cooled to 0°. The solid separated was filtered, washed several times with ether, recrystallised from benzene-petrol mixture and finally dried *in vacuo*, m.p. 120° (Found: C, 77.87; H, 6.00; N, 10.24. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$, calcd for: C, 77.56; H, 5.70; N, 10.64%).

General method of preparation of the complexes: To a solution of the ligand DTTHD (0.002 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) metal(II) perchlorate (0.002 mol) was added and the solution was refluxed for 5 h, cooled and filtered. The resulting microcrystalline solid was filtered, washed with water and ether

and finally dried *in vacuo* at 100°. The analytical data of the complexes (Table 1) confirm the 1 : 1 stoichiometry for metal-ligand.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Complex	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)	
	Metal	N
[Ni(DTTHD)](ClO ₄) ₂	7.30 (7.49)	7.00 (7.15)
[Cu(DTTHD)](ClO ₄) ₂	7.62 (7.51)	6.97 (7.14)
[Co(DTTHD)](ClO ₄) ₂	7.94 (8.05)	7.04 (7.10)

Results and Discussion

The electronic spectrum of the ligand recorded in benzene solvent, indicated two peaks at 27 100 and 38 910 cm⁻¹, and the molar extinction coefficient was found to be 3 651 cm⁻¹ mol⁻¹. These bands are assigned to the transitions $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, respectively. The ir spectra of the ligand showed very strong absorptions at 1 670 (C=O) and at 1 630 cm⁻¹ (C=N). The weak band due to C—H stretch is observed at 3 040 cm⁻¹. The medium absorptions appearing in the region 1 580–1 600 cm⁻¹ are attributed to the combination of C=C and C=N frequencies. The disappearance of the free NH₂ absorption of the starting material coupled with the analytical data has confirmed that the 2 : 1 condensation of the hydrazone with the acetylacetone has indeed taken place.

The nmr spectrum of the ligand recorded in CDCl₃/TMS showed aromatic multiplets in the region δ 7.2–8.0 and methyl and methylene signals at δ 1.66 and 2.06, respectively. This is in accordance with the values expected from the ligands of similar type⁹. The mass spectrum exhibited the molecular ion peak (M^+) at m/z 526, thus supporting the proposed molecular formula for the ligand.

The metal chelate obtained from this ligand are expected to be quite stable as in the case of Schiff base complexes derived from acetylacetone due to the polarisation of ligand electrons and the formation of M-L π -bond.

The conductance values (125–150 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹) of all the complexes in DMF show their 2 : 1 electrolyte nature¹⁰. The magnetic moments obtained by Gouy method give a clue to the nature of the stereochemistry around the metal ions. The nickel(II) complex was found to be paramagnetic with a magnetic moment of 3.2 B.M., while copper(II) complex showed a value of 1.8 B.M. The esr spectra recorded for the microcrystalline copper(II) and cobalt(II) complexes at room temperature show $g_{11}=2.218$, $g_2=2.048$, $A_{11}=170 \times 10^{-4}$ cm⁻¹ and $g_1=2.348$; and $g_3=2.075$, respectively.

The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded in DMF solution. A broad band at 20 833 cm⁻¹ characteristic for the square-planar

nickel(II) complexes has been observed in the case of [Ni(DTTHD)](ClO₄)₂, while [Cu(DTTHD)](ClO₄)₂ and [Co(DTTHD)](ClO₄)₂ showed broad bands at 16 500 and 15 750 cm⁻¹, respectively. A distorted planar geometry can be envisaged for these complexes.

The ir spectra of the complexes indicate a positive shift of 10–15 cm⁻¹ in the case of both C=O and C=N frequencies, thus confirming the N₂O₂ coordination in these complexes. The perchlorate absorption in the 1 100 cm⁻¹ region is also observed.

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Complexes of *p*-Chlorophenyloxythiosemicarbazide with Manganese(II), Iron(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II), Cadmium(II) and Mercury(II)

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THE ligands having —N—C=S group with nitrogen and sulphur as donor sites have been the subject of two reviews^{1,2}. Thiosemicarbazide exists in two tautomeric forms I and II^{3,4}. As the

